

Identification industry - university - research cooperation partners with paper and patent data

Xin Zhang¹, Haiyun Xu², Chuanyang Yang³

¹ zhangxin@clas.ac.cn

Chengdu Library and Information Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences,
No. 289, Qunxian South Street, Tianfu new area, Chengdu, (China)

² xuhaiyunnemo@gmail.com

Shandong University of Technology,
No. 88, Gongqingtuan West Road, Zibo, (China)

³ 745161221@163.com

Sichuan University,
No. 24, South Section 1, Yihuan Road, Chengdu, (China)

Abstract

Over the past few years, the science and technology sector in China has experienced rapid growth, with the output of scientific and technological achievements, such as papers and patents, ranking second in the world. However, the transformation of these achievements into practical applications remains insufficient. This paper aims to address this issue by summarizing the current methods of identifying industry-university-research cooperation partners. Starting with the industry-university-research entities, this paper analyses the internal attributes of institutions and the relationships between them, proposing a method to identify potential cooperation partners. Using the field of genetic engineering vaccines as a case study, the attributes and structural characteristics of paper and patent cooperation networks are analyzed, and the proposed method of identifying cooperative partners is verified. The results indicate that by analyzing the capabilities of industry, university, and research institutions, as well as the characteristics of the cooperation network, the node pairs' similarity can be better identified by combining attribute features and structural features to identify potential cooperation partners.

Introduction

Nowadays, the number of scientific research achievements such as papers and patents increases rapidly. However, the transformation of these achievements into practical application is still insufficient (Xu et al. 2022), and the promotion of production needs to be further improved. The inappropriate connection between theory and application has always been a hindrance to the transformation of scientific and technological innovation achievements into products. Specifically, enterprises hope to improve production efficiency, but they cannot find a suitable S&T innovation theory as guidance; Meanwhile the universities, research institutes, and other scientific research institutions cannot find the appropriate producer to put their science and technology (S & T) innovation achievements to practice. At present, the research and development (R & D) capacity of China's enterprises is weaker than the production capacity, at the same time universities and research institutes have strong research capabilities, but they usually do not have the corresponding large-scale production capacity. Therefore, it is very important to strengthen the collaborative innovation among the innovation entities.

To carry out the collaborative innovation, the primary task is to find a suitable partner for each innovation institution, so it is necessary to identify potential cooperative partners through appropriate identification methods. An effective identification method of industry-university-research cooperation partner can effectively promote the transformation and implementation of S&T innovation achievements by significantly promoting the complementary ability of different innovation subjects, improving their resource utilization rate, and helping them cope

with complex and diverse collaborative innovation environment. Therefore, it is of great significance to research the identification methods of the cooperative partners of industry, university, and research institute for promoting the transformation of scientific and technological achievements into the productivity.

This paper is divided into five parts. Part one introduces the current research status. Part two proposes the main prediction model, with Figure 1 presenting the overall framework and Table 1 presenting the structural similarity indices in the model. Part three presents an exploratory analysis of the data, with Figures 2 to 4 showing the amount of data, the distribution of institution types, and the current cooperation status. Tables 2, 3, and 4 reveal the structural indices of the cooperation network and main topic words in this field. Part four presents the results and explanations, with Table 5 showing the accuracy and optimal parameters of the model, and Tables 6 and 7 presenting the prediction results on the paper and patent data, respectively. Additionally, Table 8 shows the bridge model between paper and patent. Finally, part five summarizes the work and proposes future research directions.

Research status

At present, most of the researches on the identification cooperative partner is the application research of the specific identification method, which is usually based on specific problems, puts forward targeted identification methods and hypotheses of industry-university-research cooperation partners, and selects appropriate empirical fields for empirical research with the help of the network analysis method. At the same time, some researches focus on the theoretical induction of identification methods of industry-university-research cooperation partners.

Yoon and Song (2014) proposed a systematic method to explore the potential cooperative partners of open innovation. The proposed approach utilizes patent information that is considered the most effective data to investigate innovation activities by applying morphology analysis (MA) and generative topology map (GTM) to the process to identify the configurations of technologies and visualize the collected patent information. Based on the innovation chain theory, using multi-source data, Xu et al. (2018) obtained the core network of existing collaboration networks and institutional competitiveness in the innovation chain by combining bibliometrics and econometric analysis. On this basis, combined with the law of scientific research cooperation and economic factors, a new method to identify potential industry-university-research cooperation (IURC) partners is proposed, and the real situation of IURC cooperation is simulated. Park et al. (2015) explored potential R & D partners with the help of patent information and regarded potential R & D partners as a patent assignee hierarchy based on the technical similarity between patents by using the network analysis method. In this paper, two analysis methods of literature coupling analysis and semantic similarity are used to measure the technical similarity, and Park et al. (2015) choose the field of fuel cell membrane electrode assembly technology to explain the proposed method. Wang et al. (2017) proposed a process of R & D partner identification based on solution similarity. A topic data set containing a problem and a quantitative data set containing related subject words are selected to extract the subject-action-object semantic structure in the problem and solution (P & S) pattern, and each subject is taken as the object to determine various solutions to technical problems. Besides, this paper provides the relevant mapping to visualize text characters and identify R & D partners, and verifies the effectiveness of this method by taking dye-sensitized solar cells as an example.

Based on the characteristics of each innovation subject in the innovation chain, Xu et al. (2017) put forward a theoretical hypothesis to identify potential partners of industry-university-research in the innovation chain model. Wang et al. (2018) analysed the characteristics of

different modes of industry-university-research cooperation and different institutional entities in the same model and conducted empirical tests. The results show that the potential industry-university-research cooperation institutions can be better identified by analysing the capacity differences of industry-university-research cooperation institutions. Wang et al. (2019) explored the cooperation potential among production subjects, universities, and research institutions with the help of institutional cooperation networks at the level of papers and patents and identified of the key nodes, future cooperation hotspots, and partners of graphene at the paper level and patent level after using social network analysis method to study the key indicators of the global network, and the Latent Dirichlet Allocation topic model to analyse the research hotspots and corresponding research institutions at the paper level and patent level, and the entropy weight method and link prediction to evaluate the potential industry-university-research cooperation partners and their corresponding cooperation topics. Fu et al. (2018) established a method index system, based on the consistency between the target users of sci-tech novelty retrieval institutions and the entities of the industry - university- research institutes cooperation, to predict the potential partners of production entities, universities, and research institutions. Taking the field of bioscience as an example, this paper shows that the institutions in different stages of production - university - research have greater potential of cooperation for the specific topics research at the provincial level. Xu et al. (2021) utilized both threshold indicators and reference indicators to identify emerging research topics and classify them into different cooperation patterns.

Based on the above analysis, this article will explore the impact of different institutional attributes on industry-university-research cooperation based on the integration and analysis of a large amount of scientific and technical literature data, and propose a method for identifying potential industry-university-research cooperation partners. Finally, the feasibility of the above method will be verified by taking the genetic engineering vaccine field in the biomedical industry of China as an example.

Construction of partner recognition model

The relationship between institutional attribute information and industry-university-research cooperation

Whether the various institutional entities in the innovation chain can successfully "hold hands" and form a stable cooperation relationship depends largely on the attributes of the innovation entities (such as research hotspots, geographical location, etc.) and the relationships among various entities based on these attributes.

The research topic is one of the internal factors of the cooperation between innovation entities. As far as innovation entities are concerned, the purpose of carrying out industry-university-research cooperation is to enable the cooperation partners to obtain benefits and achieve efficiency improvement. Based on the desire for such a vision, the innovation entity will have the initial cooperation intention and then form the actual cooperation behaviour. From the perspective of research topics, institutions with similar research topics are more likely to communicate with each other in journals or conferences on related topics and thus form a relation of industry - university - research cooperation which more likely benefits all the partners. And once any difficulties are encountered in the cooperation, each entity is more likely to make full use of its advantages in the related subject area to solve the problem, and the similar research results can be found in the paper of Wang et al. (2018) and Xu et al. (2016).

Geographical location is also one of the inherent attributes of innovation entities. Considering the importance of "people" in the industry - university - research cooperation, the geo-graphical

distance has a certain impact on the personnel cooperation between the different institutes. Institutions with closer geographic locations have lower time and economic costs for personnel interaction (such as academic exchanges) and are more likely to have the intention of cooperation due to the increasing mutual understanding through easier exchanges which will help them discover potential industry-university-research cooperation opportunities. Related scholars have also made arguments for this. For example, Wen (2012) found that institutions with closer spatial and geographical locations had greater opportunities for industry-university-research cooperation with the quantitative analysis of the cooperation relationship and cooperation model between inventors and patentees, as well as the knowledge exchanges; Xu et al.(2017) analysed the promotion effect of spatial location on industry-university-research cooperation based on the innovation chain theory and the knowledge spill over effect of industry-university-research cooperation.

Based on the above analysis, this article takes the research theme of the institution and the influence of spatial location into consideration in the process of identifying the industry - university - research cooperation partner. As shown in Figure 1, the research topics of the organization are represented by key-words group, and the similarity of research topics is measured by the keyword co-occurrence relationship. If the location of one institution is adjacent to the other or the keywords co-occur, then the possibility of cooperation between the two is higher than that of institutions without the above relationship.

Figure 1 the Institution attribute and cooperation

Link prediction model based on attributed

Based on the analysis of the capabilities of industry-university-research entities and the cooperation network, link prediction methods are used to explore how to identify potential partners of industry-university-research cooperation. In this paper, nodes represent innovation entities, and edges represent relationships between entities, and the link prediction is essentially a prediction of edges that are missing in the network or edges that do not currently exist and may appear in the future. Newman (2004) first used network analysis in scientific research cooperation. Liben-Nowell and Kleinberg (2007) proposed the link prediction problem in social networks, and they performed similarity predication based on the method of defining the nodes according to the structural characteristics of the network. R Guns and R Rousseau (2014) constructed a weighted cooperative network of malaria and tuberculosis to conduct cooperative prediction and recommendation. Yan et al. (2014) used papers from 59 journals in the field of library and information as an empirical study to compare the different prediction results of various indicators. Zhang et al (2018), Yu et al (2018) used network representation learning to predict the scientific research cooperation partners at the author level.

Current research on cooperation partners identification methods based on the link prediction mostly concern about network structural features, or institutional attributes, lacking the integration of structural and attribute features, or only integrating single category attributes like text, and lacking the integration of multiple heterogeneous attributes. This paper proposes a node similarity measurement fusing multiple heterogeneous attributes, and assume that $G=G(V, E, A)$, V is the node set, which represents the institutions in the paper and patent industry-university-research cooperation network; E is the edge set, which represents the cooperative relationship between institutions in the cooperative network; A is the attribute mapping, $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$, representing different types (n) of attributes. In this article, A includes two attributes: research topic and geographic location, and then the similarity of nodes can be represented by equation (1).

$$sim(V_i, V_j) = (1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i) structureSim(V_i, V_j) + \alpha_i \sum_{i=1}^n attributeSim(V_i, V_j) \quad (1)$$

(1) Structure Similarity

There are many indicators that characterize the structural similarity of nodes on the network, such as common neighbor (CN), cosine similarity, Jaccard indicator, Adamic-Adar (AA) indicator, resource allocation (RP) indicator, LHN-I indicator, local path indicator (LP), Katz indicator, restart random walk, et al. Zhou et al. (2009) compared 9 similarity measurement indicators and proposed an indicator based on resource allocation (RA). The experiments in his paper show that the RA indicator is better than others in some networks. Four famous methods are selected to represent the structural similarity of the nodes. As for two nodes u and v in the network, let $\Gamma(v)$ be the neighbor set of node v , then the similar measure in those methods can be described in Table I.

Table 1. Basic structure similarity measure model

<i>Method</i>	<i>Description</i>
Resource Allocation Index (RA)	The RA index of nodes u, v is defined as $\sum_{w \in \Gamma(u) \cap \Gamma(v)} \Gamma(w)^{-1}$
Jaccard Coefficient (JC)	The JC score of nodes u, v is defined as $(\Gamma(u) \cap \Gamma(v)) / (\Gamma(u) \cup \Gamma(v))$
Adamic Adar Index (AA)	The AA index of nodes u, v is defined as $\sum_{w \in \Gamma(u) \cap \Gamma(v)} (\log \Gamma(w))^{-1}$
Preferential Attachment (PA)	The PA score of nodes u, v is defined as $ \Gamma(u) \Gamma(v) $

(2) Attribute Similarity

This article involves two attributes, namely, research topic and geographic location.

① Topic similarity. This paper adopts the method of cosine similarity to measure the research topics similarity between different institutions. Let C_u be the topic vector of node u , representing the research topic vector of institution u , the topic similarity can be defined as (2).

$$topicSim(u, v) = \text{cossim}(C_u, C_v) = \frac{\langle C_u, C_v \rangle}{\|C_u\| \|C_v\|} \quad (2)$$

② Geographical similarity. This paper uses the Euclidean distance between different cities where the institution is located, at the level of the longitude and latitude, to characterize the similarity of location. Let d_v be the city where the institution v is located, (la_v, lo_v) be the latitude and longitude of city v , then the distance and geographical similarity between (u, v) can be defined as (3) and (4).

$$d(u, v) \approx ((la_u - la_v)^2 + (lo_u - lo_v)^2)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$geoSim(u, v) = (1 + d(u, v))^{-1} \quad (4)$$

Empirical analysis: A case study of genetic engineering vaccine

Field selection and data sources

Field selection

As a strategic frontier, the biomedical industry has attracted more and more attention from various countries and is expected to become a major pillar of the global economy. In 2016, the State Council issued the "Thirteenth Five-Year" National Strategic Emerging Industry Development Plan and pointed out the key position of the biomedical industry in the future industrial development of China. Gene engineered vaccine (GEV) as a new type of vaccine, has been discussed more by the society in recent years, and has an increasingly important position in the vaccine industry, and its main types include protein engineering vaccines, gene deletion live vaccines, nucleic acid vaccines, etc. Among the emerging industries of science and technology, the field of biomedicine is distinct from the others with its obvious characteristic of industry-university-research cooperation. As a high-end segment of biomedicine, there are a large number of papers and patents on GEV and the results of recent years have accounted for a large proportion, which can meet the needs of the empirical work while taking into account the timeliness. Based on the above reasons, this study chooses the field of GEV as the field of empirical analysis. The number of papers and patents related to GEV in China is experiencing rapid growth, which we have closely monitored. To provide more comprehensive insights into our model outputs, we have incorporated Chinese papers and patents as empirical data.

Data description

The Web of Science of Clarivate Analytics is selected as the literature source of this field, and the Derwent Innovation Index is selected as the source of patent literature in this field. The number of retrieved papers and patent data is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The time distribution of global and Chinese paper and patent

As for China, the earliest patent application for genetic engineering vaccine appeared in 1992. The number of patents has been growing steadily since 1998, and the growth rate has been accelerating since 2006. Although there were some fluctuations during the period from 1998 to

2006, the overall growth rate was fast, and the number reached the peak in 2017 (131 records). The earliest papers on related fields in China appeared in 1990, and the number increased significantly until 2000. There were some fluctuations during the period (from 2005 to 2018), but the overall trend was upward, and the number reached the highest point (46 papers) in 2018.

After comparing the two types of documents, it is found that the number of patents is significantly higher than the number of papers, and the growth rate of patents at the rapid growth period is slightly slower than that of papers. The reason is that there is a process of "divergence" from papers to patents: that is, multiple patents are based on the same theoretical result, which occurs more frequently than "a patent comes from multiple theoretical foundations", causing the appearance of the number of patents being obviously more than that of papers at the same time.

Subject identification

(a) The proportion of research entities in papers (b) The proportion of research entities in patents

Figure 3. The proportion of research entities in papers or patents in China

Figure 3 is a pie chart of the proportions of various institutions in the paper and patent cooperation network of China. The way of type classification is adopted by the method of keyword matching of institution names. As shown in the figure, universities and colleges account for the largest proportion of paper collaboration network, with a total number of 154, accounting for 44% of the total number of institutions, indicating that universities are still the largest subjects in the field of GEV in China. The number of scientific research institutions (51), hospitals (56) and enterprises (56) are similar, accounting for 14%, 16%, 16% of the total respectively, showing that these three types of subjects also play an important role in the field of GEV. Although the number of scientific research institutions is not so much as others, the average number of papers issued by each institution is relatively larger, which reflects that China's scientific research institutions also have strong overall scientific research capacity.

In the patent cooperation network, enterprises account for half of the total number of institutions, showing the enthusiasm of enterprises to put patents into practice is stronger than that of writing papers, which is in line with the profit-oriented development model of enterprises. Universities and research institutes are still the backbone of patent application in the field of GEV. Besides, the number of patent applications in hospitals decreased significantly compared with that of papers.

Data description and analysis

Based on the institution-institution co-occurrence matrix at the paper level, the VOSViewer analysis software is used to generate the industry-university-research institution cooperation network at the level of paper and patent respectively, as shown in Figure 4.

(a) At paper level institution cooperation network

(b) At patent level institution cooperation network

Figure 4 the Visualization of cooperation network

The indicators of the two networks separately are calculated by Gephi in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of cooperation network indicators between papers and patent institutions

<i>Index</i>	<i>Paper cooperation network</i>	<i>Patent cooperation network</i>
# Nodes	331	532
# Edges	679	123
Max degree	45 (Chinese Acad Sci) 32 (Acad Mil Med Sci) 30 (Chinese Acad Agr Sci) 28 (Fudan Univ) 23 (Peking Univ)	4 (Acad Mil Med Sci) 4 (Univ Xiamen) 4 (Shenzhen Inst Adv Tech)
Avg. degree	2.051	0.231
Weighted avg. degree	2.417	0.295
Diameter	10	4
Density	0.012	0.001
Modularity	0.702	0.967
#Connected components	53	430
Avg. clustering coefficient	0.688	0.77
Avg. path length	3.905	1.339

As shown in Figure 4, the nodes represent industry-university-research institutions, the size of nodes indicates the frequency of institutions appearing in the data set, the connection between nodes indicates the cooperation between institutions, and the thickness of connections indicates the strength of cooperation. It can be seen from Figure 4 (a) and Table II that the largest node in the paper cooperation network is the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), and the number of connections between CAS and other institutions is also larger than others, indicating that CAS is at the core of the paper level cooperation. In addition to the CAS, the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, the Chinese Academy of Military Medical Sciences, as well as some top universities of China such as Peking University and Fudan University, are noted in the paper cooperation network, which indicates that these institutions have a large number of papers and cooperation. And this also reflects that China still relies on these top universities and research institutions to publish and co-publish papers in the field of GEV. On the whole, the nodes in the cooperation network of industry-university-research institutions at the level of the paper are more centralized, and the more cooperative relations between nodes there are, the higher the network density is.

It can be seen from Figure 4(b) and Table II, compared with the cooperation network of paper, the nodes in the cooperation network of patents are more dispersed, and the degrees and connections are smaller, and there is no particularly prominent institution. The reason is that compared with the paper, the patent is influenced by the economic benefits. In the institutional cooperation of papers, there are usually no big differences between the two parties on the distribution of research results, and there are few cases involving the distribution of economic benefits. In contrast, patent achievements are often linked to economic benefits. Due to the different views on the distribution of patent ownership and the way of liquidation, it is easy to break the cooperation. Considering this, many institutions would rather obtain exclusive patents and benefits through independent research and development than share the economic benefits behind patents with others. Besides, compared with the paper, the time of patent transforming

into economic benefits is shorter, and the benefits behind it are more easily seen by enterprises. And driven by interests, enterprises are more inclined to invest their resources into the patent application. On the whole, patent cooperation is loose, and the cooperation relationship is less than the paper network.

By analyzing the co-occurrence matrix, we can find the relationship between the research topic and the industry-university-research cooperation, and using the Derwent Data Analyzer (DDA) tool, we get the institution-institution co-occurrence matrix and institution-topic co-occurrence matrix at the level of paper and patent respectively. In the institution-institution co-occurrence matrix of paper, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS) and its top three cooperation institutions are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. TOP 3 Paper Cooperation institutions with CAAS

<i>Order</i>	<i>Institution name</i>	<i>Cooperation frequency</i>
1	Academy Military Medicine Sciences	4
2	Chinese Agricultural University	4
3	Jilin Agricultural University	4

In the institution-topic words co-occurrence matrix of paper, the first five topics corresponding to the above institutions are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Top 5 keywords of institutions

	<i>Chin Acad Agr Sci</i>	<i>Acad Mil Med Sci</i>	<i>China Agr Univ</i>	<i>Jilin Agr Univ</i>
1	DNA vaccine (13)	DNA vaccine (7)	DNA vaccine (3)	DNA vaccine (3)
2	foot-and-mouth disease virus (10)	T cells (3)	fusion protein (2)	immune response (2)
3	protective immunity (9)	balb/c mice (3)	recombinant virus (2)	IFN gamma (2)
4	immune response (8)	control groups (3)	respiratory syndrome virus (2)	toxoplasma gondii (2)
5	respiratory syndrome virus (8)	fusion protein (2)	toxoplasma gondii (2)	protective immunity (1)

As can be seen from Table IV, the five keywords that appear most frequently in the CAAS are DNA vaccine (13 times), foot-and-mouth disease virus (10 times), protective immunity (9 times), immune response (8 times), and respiratory syndrome virus (8 times).

As the main cooperative institutions of the CAAS, the five keywords that appear most frequently in the PLA Academy of Military Medical Sciences are DNA vaccine (7 times), T cells (3 times), balb/c mice (3 times), control groups (3 times) and fusion protein (2 times). Among them, DNA vaccine is also the first keyword of the CAAS. The top 5 keywords that appear most frequently in China Agricultural University are DNA vaccine (3 times), fusion protein (2 times), recombinant virus (2 times), respiratory syndrome virus (2 times), and toxoplasma gondii (2 times). Among them, DNA vaccine and respiratory syndrome virus are the first and fifth keywords of the CAAS. The top 5 keywords that appear most frequently in Jilin Agricultural University are DNA vaccine (3 times), immune response (2 times), IFN

gamma (2 times), toxoplasma gondii (2 times), and protective immunity (1 time). Among them, DNA vaccine, immune response and protective immunity are the first, fourth and third keywords of the CAAS.

Through the above analysis, it can be seen that institutions with similar research topics are more likely to cooperate with each other. The similarity of research topics has a positive impact on the industry-university-research cooperation. The closer the research topics are, the more likely the cooperation between institutions will be.

The density of patent cooperation network is lower than that of paper cooperation network, and the relationship between topic words and industry-university-research cooperation in the co-occurrence matrix is not as obvious as that in paper, but it is in line with the rule that "institutions with similar research topics have greater possibility of cooperation".

Cooperation partners identification results

Using the identification method proposed in part III section B, we can predict the science and research cooperation results at the level of paper and patent respectively.

Fusion parameter selection and model evaluation

In this paper, the link prediction problem is transformed into a binary classification problem with/without links. First of all, according to the ratio of 0.5, 0.3 and 0.2, the edge set is divided into training set, verification set and test set respectively, and then taking the training set as the baseline, we take the edges in the validation set as positive samples, randomly generate the same number of negative samples, apply the model calculation results, take the AUC value as the objective function, and use the Bayesian optimization method to calculate the optimal fusion parameter values. On the other hand, the test set is processed in the same way, and the same number of negative samples as the test edge set is randomly generated, and finally the optimal fusion parameters (calculated in the verification set) are used to evaluate the model.

We use the AUC, ROC_AUC and F1_Score indicators to evaluate the model. The AUC indicator is the most commonly used indicator to evaluate the link prediction problem. Provided the rank of all non-observed links, the AUC value can be interpreted as the probability that a randomly chosen missing link is given a higher score than a randomly chosen non-existent link. The AUC value ranges from 0.5 to 1. The AUC value of random allocation method is 0.5, and the AUC value of perfect prediction is 1. The closer the AUC value is to 1, the better the model effect is, and the ROC_AUC is defined as the area under the ROC curve in the binary classification problem, while the F1_Score is the balance of precision and recall in the binary classification problem.

Besides, the Bayesian optimization is chosen to select the optimal fusion parameter of structure similarity (α_s), topic similarity (α_t) and geographical similarity (α_g). Let $\alpha = (\alpha_s, \alpha_t, \alpha_g)$, for each α , the fusion function is brought into the calculation, and an AUC value can be obtained. Therefore, the AUC value can correspond to the function of the parameter α , which is recorded as $AUC(\alpha)$. The optimization goal is to select the fusion hyperparameter α value that maximizes the $AUC(\alpha)$ value, and the basic idea of Bayes optimization is to estimate the posterior distribution of the objective function based on the Gauss process hypothesis and the observation data D , as a result this article uses Python's Bayes_Opt tool.

At last, the best performance fusion parameter of paper cooperation network α and the evaluation results in the test set are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Parameter selection in paper cooperation network

<i>Method</i>	<i>Parameter</i> ($\alpha_s, \alpha_t, \alpha_g$)	<i>ROC_AUC</i>	<i>F1 Score</i>	<i>AUC</i>
RA	(0.1240,0.0946,0.7814)	0.8494	0.6165	0.9070
JC	(0.1468,0.4889,0.3643)	0.8079	0.5952	0.8392
AA	(0.0837,0.7624,0.1539)	0.8712	0.6106	0.9163
PA	(0.4232,0.3161,0.2607)	0.8454	0.7532	0.8475

In this case, the effects of RA, AA, and PA have no big difference, and the JC method is slightly inferior. After parameter selection, they can all make cooperative predictions well. In comparison, the AA has the highest ROC, and the PA has the highest F1 score. The RA algorithm is relatively balanced in all indicators, and the following parts are results using RA as for example.

Prediction results

Tables 6 shows the groups of institutions with the highest probability of cooperation in the paper cooperation network with Resource Allocation Index and best selection parameter ($\alpha_s, \alpha_t, \alpha_g$) = (0.1240, 0.0946, 0.7814).

Table 6. The Prediction results of paper cooperation network

<i>Institution A</i>	<i>Institution B</i>	<i>Weight</i>
Peking Univ	Beijing 302 Hosp	1.3192
Beijing Ditan Hosp	Beijing 302 Hosp	1.3039
Chinese Acad Med Sci	Peking Union Med Coll	1.2396
Jilin Univ	Acad Mil Med Sci PLA	1.0000
Nanjing 2nd Hosp	Nanjing PLA 81 Hosp	0.9489
Chinese Acad Agr Sci	South China Agr Univ	0.9158
Peking Univ	Beijing Ditan Hosp	0.9066
Shandong Prov Key Lab Anim Biotechnol & Dis Contr	Taian Cent Hosp	0.8957
Natl Taiwan Univ	Natl Taiwan Univ Hosp	0.8870
Shandong Agr Univ	Shandong Prov Key Lab Anim Biotechnol & Dis Contr	0.8755
Chengdu Med Coll	Sichuan Prov Sch Hlth	0.8529
Natl Chung Hsing Univ	Taichung Vet Gen Hosp	0.8428
Guangdong Pharmaceut Univ	Guangdong Prov Key Lab Biotechnol Candidate Drug	0.8415
Hubei Acad Agr Sci	Hubei Key Lab Anim Embryo & Mol Breeding	0.8415
Hainan Univ	Hainan Prov Nongken Gen Hosp	0.8364
Acad Mil Med Sci	Beijing 302 Hosp	0.8315
Fudan Univ	Beijing 302 Hosp	0.8270
Natl Taiwan Univ	Natl Yang Ming Univ	0.8215
Acad Mil Med Sci	Jiangsu Prov Peoples Hosp	0.8204
Fudan Univ	Jiangsu Prov Peoples Hosp	0.8159

The highest similarity is 1.3192, for the cooperation between the Beijing 302 Hospital and Peking University. 302 Hospital is called the 302th Hospital of the Chinese People's Liberation

Army. In 2002, Peking University and 302 Hospital established a joint personnel training mechanism, incorporated 302 Hospital into its teaching hospital system, and assumed teaching tasks for some medical specialties. They have in-depth cooperation in biosafety and infectious disease prevention.

Beijing Ditan Hospital, formerly known as Beijing No. 1 Infectious Disease Hospital, has strong capabilities in infectious disease research and treatment. 302 Hospital is the country's largest tertiary hospital for infectious diseases. Epidemiology is the main research field shared by both. Ditan Hospital is also one of the teaching hospitals of the Peking University Health Science Center.

Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences (CAMS) and Peking Union Medical College (PUMC) has close connection as well. PUMC was incorporated into the CAMS in 1957 and is now under the integrated management with the CAMS.

The Medical Department of Jilin University has a close relationship with the PLA General Hospital (301 Hospital). In the early days of the founding of the People's Republic of China, the Medical Department of Jilin University was named the First Military Medical University of the Chinese People's Liberation Army.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that the cooperative institutions predicted in Table IV have various linkages that are beneficial to cooperation, and each pair of institutions has a great cooperation probability.

Table 7 shows the prediction results of the patent cooperation network with Resource Allocation Index and one of the best parameter $(\alpha_s, \alpha_t, \alpha_g) = (0.8373, 0.0804, 0.0823)$. It can be seen that the similarity of the prediction results is not so much as that of the paper cooperation network, and the reason is that the paper cooperation network has more edges and larger density than the patent cooperation network. The patent cooperation network is sparser, so the predicted similarity is lower. The prediction results in the patent cooperation network show that the cooperation tends to be formed between affiliated entities such as some research institutes and their affiliated companies, enterprise groups and their subsidiaries, or companies with investment relations. The frequency and scope of patent agency cooperation are lower than that of paper cooperation.

Table 7. the Prediction results of patent cooperation network

<i>Institution A</i>	<i>Institution B</i>	<i>Weight</i>
Beijing Dabeinong Sci & Technology Group	Beijing Kemufeng Biological Pharm Co Ltd	0.7144
Shenzhen Inst Advanced Technology, CAS	Syz Cell Therapy Co	0.6667
Shenzhen Inst Advanced Technology, CAS	Shenzhen Yuanzheng Cell Medical Technolo	0.6667
Shenzhen Inst Advanced Technology, CAS	Hryz Biotech Co	0.6667
Beijing Dabeinong Sci & Technology Group	Fuzhou Da Bei Nong Biotech Co Ltd	0.6667
Beijing Dabeinong Sci & Technology Group	Beijing Dabeinong Technology Group Co	0.6667

Beijing Kemufeng Biological Pharm Co Ltd	Fuzhou Da Bei Nong Biotech Co Ltd	0.6667
Beijing Kemufeng Biological Pharm Co Ltd	Beijing Dabeinong Technology Group Co	0.6667
Fuzhou Da Bei Nong Biotech Co Ltd	Beijing Dabeinong Technology Group Co	0.6667
Anbote Gene Eng Tech Co Ltd Beijing	Dongguan Haofa Biotechnology Development	0.6667
Anbote Gene Eng Tech Co Ltd Beijing	Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Lt	0.6667
Anbote Gene Eng Tech Co Ltd Beijing	Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Ltd	0.6667
Dongguan Haofa Biotechnology Development	Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Lt	0.6667
Dongguan Haofa Biotechnology Development	Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Ltd	0.6667
Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Lt	Beijing Abt Genetic Eng Technology Co Ltd	0.6667
Syz Cell Therapy Co	Shenzhen Yuanzheng Cell Medical Technolo	0.5833
Syz Cell Therapy Co	Hryz Biotech Co	0.5833
Shenzhen Yuanzheng Cell Medical Technolo	Hryz Biotech Co	0.5833

Bridge institutions in cooperation networks

Bridging institutions refer to those have cooperation with others in both paper and patent cooperation networks. Bridging institutions are an important bridge between basic research and applied research. Through the algorithm of this article, the bridge mechanism can be used to make predictions from basic to application. Table 8 shows the potential cooperation institutions of Xiamen University, and the numbers in brackets represent for the cooperation weight with Xiamen University obtained by the method proposed in Part III B. With Xiamen University as a bridge institution, more institutions in the field of basic research and applied research can form predicted cooperation links, with potential cooperation chances.

Table 8. The bridge institution

<i>Paper Cooperation Institutions</i>	<i>Bridge Institution</i>	<i>Patent Cooperation Institutes</i>
Fisheries Res Inst Fujian (0.5375)	Xiamen University	Xiamen Waitai Canghai Biotechnology Co (0.5000)
Shantou Univ Med Coll (0.2308)		Xiamen Innovax Biotech Co Ltd (0.5000)
Fujian Agr & Forestry Univ (0.2120)		Yangshengtang Co Ltd (0.5000)
Fuzhou Infect Dis Hosp (0.2120)		Yangsheng Tang Ltd (0.5000)
Fujian Med Uni (0.2054)		
Natl Def Med Ctr (0.2012)		

Summary and prospect

It is an important way to promote the transformation efficiency of S&T achievements into practical application and to improve social productivity by carrying out industry-university-research cooperation and strengthening collaborative innovation among innovation entities. Based on the existing research on industry-university-research cooperation, this paper studies the partner recognition method of industry-university-research cooperation based on papers and patents.

First of all, starting from the relevant literature, this paper summarizes, and reviews the current research status in the field of industry-university-research cooperation partner identification, and puts forward the research direction. Secondly, it analyses the relationship between the internal attributes of institutional entities and industry-university-research cooperation, and proposes a method for identifying potential industry-university-research cooperation partners that combines structural features with multiple heterogeneous attributes. Then, using GEV as an empirical field, it analyses the structure and characteristics of papers and patent industry-university-research cooperation networks, and finally verifies the potential cooperative partner identification method proposed in this paper after analysing the impact of research topics and other factors on scientific cooperation.

This research has certain theoretical significance for enriching and perfecting the current identification methods of potential industry-university-research cooperation partners, and has certain practical significance for the future development of industry-university-research collaborative innovation and strategic decision-making deployment in related fields.

Nevertheless, this research has certain limitations due to various factors, including research conditions. As such, future research directions are proposed to further advance our understanding of the topic.

(1) Expand the field of empirical research. In the empirical analysis part, this article selects the field of GEV for its good representativeness. GEV is a hot frontier in the field of biomedicine, and related studies have shown that in the emerging technology industries, the field of biomedicine is distinct from the others with its obvious characteristic of industry-university-research cooperation. However, due to the limited research conditions, only one professional field is selected for empirical research. In the following research, we can find more representative fields as empirical partners for analysis.

(2) Analysis of additional influencing factors. While this paper considers several potential driving factors for industry-university-research cooperation, there are many other factors that may also have an impact. To achieve even more accurate predictions, future research could incorporate more complex heterogeneous networks and consider a broader range of potential influencing factors. A heterogeneous information network is an information network composed of multiple types of nodes and links. It can integrate more types of partners and their complex interactions, while also containing richer semantic information. In future research, more heterogeneous information can be introduced into the papers and patents industry-university-research cooperation networks, and heterogeneous network analysis can be conducted to further explore the relationship between papers and patents at different levels.

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